

Molybdenum blue method for the spectrophotometric determination of acetazolamide and piracetam

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Abstract : A novel method for the spectrophotometric determination of acetazolamide and piracetam in pharmaceutical formulations using molybdenum blue complex formation was developed by the authors. Aqueous and acidic solutions of the drug sample of acetazolamide on reaction with ammonium molybdate solution and hydrazine sulphate solution gave a clear, stable and intense blue colored molybdenum blue complex. This molybdenum blue showed a λ_{\max} at 830 nm for the aqueous solution of the drug sample and at 824.5 nm for the acidic solution of the drug sample. Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range 0–80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for the former and 0–40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for the latter. Aqueous solution of the drug sample of piracetam on reaction with 2.5% ammonium molybdate solution and 0.15% hydrazine sulphate solution followed by heating, an intense blue colored product was developed, which showed a λ_{\max} at 830 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range of 0–60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The method was found to be accurate, precise and simple. The method is important in view of the fact that the excess dosage causes clinical problems and optimum dosage has to be fixed in the use of the drug.

Keywords : Acetazolamide, piracetam, spectrophotometry, molybdenum blue, ammonium molybdate, hydrazine sulphate.

Introduction

Acetazolamide *N*-(5-sulfamoyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)acetamide is categorized as a carbonic anhydrase inhibitor.

It is used in the treatment of glaucoma, altitude sickness, cystinuria, periodic paralysis, central sleep apnea, epileptic seizures and Dural ectasia. Acetazolamide is a diuretic¹⁻⁵. Some common adverse effects of acetazolamide include paraesthesia, fatigue, drowsiness, depression, decreased libido, bitter or metallic taste, nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, diarrhea, black feces, polyuria, kidney stones, metabolic acidosis and electrolyte changes (hypokalemia, hyponatremia)⁴.

Piracetam is chemically 2-(2-oxopyrrolidin-1-

yl)acetamide with molecular weight 142.16 g/mol and with chemical formula $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$. Piracetam is a nootropic drug in the racetams group.

Piracetam is prescribed mainly for myoclonus⁶. It was also used by Janz in the 1950's for Juvenile Myoclonic Epilepsy⁷. Peripheral vascular effects of piracetam have suggested its use as potential for vertigo, dyslexia and sickle cell anemia⁸. A subsequent Cochrane review of the evidence did not support piracetam's use in sickle cell crisis prevention⁹. Piracetam may be potential for the treatment of the symptoms of childhood autism¹⁰.

Piracetam has been found to have very few side effects, which are, mild, and transient¹¹. Many other stud-

ies have likewise found piracetam to be well tolerated¹²⁻¹⁵. General excitability, anxiety, insomnia, irritation, headache, agitation, nervousness and tremor are some reported side effects of the drug piracetam¹⁶⁻¹⁸, other side effects include somnolence, weight gain, depression, weakness, increased libido and hyper exuality.

Hence quantitative determination of acetazolamide in pharmaceutical formulations thus becomes important, since it's over dosage causes ill effects. In literature¹⁹⁻²² it was found that earlier workers used UV spectroscopy for the determination of acetazolamide. Those procedures are found to be tedious and do not have serious accuracy. Molybdenum blue method is used for the determination of metals, certain bacterium etc.²³⁻²⁵.

In literature it was reported²⁶⁻³¹ that, the quantitative determination of the drug piracetam is conducted by UV spectrophotometry, capillary electrophoresis, chromatographic and electro analytical methods. Specific colour reactions are not reported in literature so far with the drug under investigation. Hence the authors attempted for a study on colour reactions of the drug with various chromogens. During this study it was found that, piracetam solution showed an intense blue color with the reaction of it and a solution of ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

All the reagents were of Merck AR grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Preparation of pure acetazolamide drug sample solution in aqueous media : An adequately weighed quantity of 0.1 g of the pure drug sample was transferred into a 250 ml beaker, and dissolved in distilled water. The mixture is heated to 60 °C for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask and standardized³².

Preparation of pure acetazolamide drug sample solution in 2 N sulphuric acid : An adequately weighed quantity of 0.1 g of the pure drug sample was transferred into

a 250 ml beaker and dissolved in 100 ml 2 N sulphuric acid. The mixture was heated to 60 °C for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask using double distilled water and standardized³².

Preparation of the pharmaceutical formulation solution : Ten tablets of acetazolamide were ground into a fine powder and from that weighed quantity of 0.1 g of the drug sample was transferred into a 250 ml beaker and dissolved in 100 ml of double distilled water. The mixture was heated to 60 °C for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask.

Another 0.1 g of the same powdered sample was weighed and transferred into a 250 ml beaker, followed by the addition of 100 ml of 2 N sulphuric acid. The mixture was heated at 60 °C for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask using double distilled water.

Preparation of the pure piracetam drug sample solution in aqueous media :

An adequately weighed quantity of the pure drug is weighed and dissolved in distilled water the resulting solution was heated to 60 °C for half an hour. After the predetermined time, the solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask and standardized³³.

Preparation of pharmaceutical formulation solution of piracetam :

Ten tablets of the drug were ground into a fine powder. From such powder, an accurately weighed quantity of the sample was dissolved in 100 ml of double distilled water and heated to 60 °C for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was made up to the mark and standardized³³.

Ammonium molybdate solution : An accurately weighed 2.5 g of ammonium molybdate was transferred into a 100

ml volumetric flask. The substance was dissolved by the addition of 10 N sulphuric acid and after complete dissolution, the resulting solution was made up to the mark using 10 N sulphuric acid³⁴.

Hydrazine sulphate aqueous solution : An accurately weighed 0.15 g of hydrazine sulphate into a 100 ml volumetric flask, was dissolved in double distilled water and after complete dissolution the resulting solution was made up to the mark³⁴.

Instruments used :

ELICO LI127 pH meter was used for the determination of pH of samples. JASCO V 750 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with matched set of quartz cuvettes (10 mm path length) were used for all the absorbance measurements.

Method I :

Recommended procedure for the determination of λ_{max} :

An aliquot of the aqueous solution of the drug sample was transferred into a 50 ml volumetric flask. To this 5 ml of ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of hydrazine sulphate solution were added and mixed well. The resulting solution was made up to the mark. This volumetric flask was heated on a water bath for 10 min. An intense blue color was developed. After the predetermined time the flask was cooled to room temperature and the absorption spectra was recorded in the wavelength range of 380–900 nm. The intense blue colored product, molybdenum blue, showed a maximum absorbance at 830 nm (Fig. 1). The same procedure was adopted for the determination of λ_{max} for the colour produced by the reaction between piracetam and the reagents specified (Fig. 4).

Recommended procedure for the determination of drug :

For the determination of acetazolamide, a series of solutions of varying concentration solutions of the drug sample were prepared by transferring 1 ml, 2 ml, 3 ml, 4 ml, 5 ml into 50 ml volumetric flasks, to each of which 5 ml of ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of hydrazine sulphate were added. The resulting solution was made

up to the mark. These volumetric flasks were heated on a water bath for ten minutes. After the predetermined time, the flasks were cooled to room temperature. An intense blue colored product was obtained, and for each of the blue coloured solution absorbance measurements were recorded at 830 nm and Beer's law plot was drawn for the same (Fig. 2).

An aliquot of the drug sample solution was transferred into a 50 ml volumetric flask, to this 5 ml of ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of hydrazine sulphate solution were added and mixed well. The resulting solution was made up to the mark using double distilled water. This flask was heated on a water bath for 10 min. An intense blue colour was developed. After the predetermined time the flask was cooled to room temperature and the absorption measurement were recorded at 830 nm. From such absorbance measurement, the concentration of the drug in the solution was determined with the help of the standard curve (Fig. 2).

The same method is used for the determination of piracetam in commercial pharmaceutical formulations (Fig. 5).

Method II :

The absorbance measurement methodology mentioned above was adopted for the drug sample solution prepared by dissolving the powdered sample of acetazolamide in 2

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the aqueous solution, and acidic solutions of the drug sample with ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate solution.

Fig. 2. Beer's law obedience plot for the aqueous solution and acidic solution of the drug acetazolamide.

N sulphuric acid too. The absorption maximum for the blue colored solution developed was found to be 824.5 nm in this case (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Piracetam does not show any colour reaction in sulphuric acid media under specified conditions.

Specificity :

The effect of excipients such as starch, lactose, magnesium stearate, titanium oxide and talc etc. was evaluated to study the specificity of the proposed method through

the analysis of a placebo solution²¹. The developed method was applied to check the interference of any of the above mentioned substances with the absorbance of the sample solution.

Linearity :

A stock solution of the drugs was prepared and made proper dilutions to give a concentration range of 2–80 µg/ml. Each solution was prepared in triplicate and linearity was determined by constructing a plot between absorbance and concentration.

Precision :

Intra-day and inter-day precisions, as per standard guidelines were determined to assess the precision of the method developed by the authors. From such data the %RSD was calculated.

Accuracy :

To the pre-analysed sample solutions, a known amount of standard stock solution was added at different levels, i.e. 80%, 100% and 120%. The solutions were reanalyzed by the proposed method.

Sensitivity :

The sensitivity of measurements of the drugs by the

Table 1. Spectral data analysis report for acetazolamide

Sr. No.	Name of the parameter	Method I	Method II
1.	Dissolution of the drug	Double distilled water	2 N sulphuric acid
2.	Colour of the product	Intense blue	Intense blue
3.	Stability of the colored product (h)	24	24
4.	λ_{max} (nm)	830	824.5
5.	Beer's law obedience (µg/ml)	0–80	0–40
6.	LOD (µg/ml)	1.23	2.00
7.	LOQ (µg/ml)	3.75	6.07
8.	Correlation	0.9995	0.8485
9.	RSD (%)	1.4	1.98

Table 2. Comparison between the standard method and method developed by authors for acetazolamide

Sr. No.	Name of the drug	Method I			Method II		
		SM ^a (mg)	MU ^b (mg)	% error	SM ^a (mg)	MA ^b (mg)	% error
1.	Acetamide	99.8	99.7	0.1	99.8	99.6	0.2
2.	Diamox	99.7	99.7	0	99.7	99.4	0.3
3.	Synomax	99.5	99.4	0.1	99.5	99.3	0.2

^aStandard method. ^bMethod developed by author.

proposed method was determined by limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ are calculated using $LOD = 3.3 \times SD/slope$ and $LOQ = 10 \times SD/slope$.

Ruggedness :

Ruggedness of the proposed method is determined for 60 µg/ml concentration of piracetam by analysis of aliquots by two analysts using same operational and environmental conditions.

Results and discussion

The complete spectral data obtained for the drug acetazolamide was presented in Table 1. A comparative table for the results obtained by the method proposed and the standard method were presented in Table 2. In the first method where the drug sample was prepared by dissolving the powdered sample in distilled water, the resulting molybdenum blue product, showed maximum absorbance at 830 nm (Fig. 1). Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range of 0–80 µg/ml (Fig. 2). Molar extinction coefficient for the same was found to be 3223.8 $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{L cm}^{-1}$. Correlation coefficient in this method was found to be 0.9982, limit of detection was found to be 1.23 µg/ml and limit of quantification was found to be 3.75 µg/ml. Relative standard deviation for ten samples was found to be 1.4% which was well within the standard value.

In the second method where the drug sample solution was prepared by dissolving the powdered sample was 2 N sulphuric acid, the resulting molybdenum blue showed maximum absorbance at 824.5 nm (Fig. 1). Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range of 0–40 µg/ml (Fig. 2). Molar extinction coefficient for the same was found to be 2500 $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{L cm}^{-1}$. Correlation coefficient in this method was found to be 0.8485, limit of detection was found to be 2.00 µg/ml and limit of quantification was found to be 6.07 µg/ml. Relative standard deviation for ten samples was found to be 1.98% which was well within the standard value.

In both the methods the reagents used were found to have no interference with the absorption spectra of the blue colored product.

Effect of concentration and volume of reagents :

Ammonium molybdate solution : The optimum concentration of ammonium molybdate solution was fixed as 2.5% (w/v) for effective reaction (Fig. 3). The optimum concentration of hydrazine sulphate solution was fixed as 0.15% (w/v) for the effective reaction. Addition of 5 ml of 2.5% ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of hydrazine sulphate solution was fixed as optimum volumes of the reagents being added to get stable, clear molybdenum blue complex.

Fig. 3. Effect of concentration on the absorbance measurements. Concentration below 2.5% (w/v) of ammonium molybdate solution, aqueous solution and acidic solution of the drug sample.

The authors found that the sample solution of the drug prepared in distilled water showed constant results when compared to that of the drug solution prepared in 2 N sulphuric acid, there by the authors conclude that the former method was advantageous than the later, as it avoids the usage of acids. Lower detection limits and quantification limits were also noticed in the former method. It was found that, drug sample dissolved in 2 N sulphuric acid and with required ammonium molybdate solution and hydrazine sulphate solution has shown a lower λ_{max} to that of the aqueous solution of the drug sample. The difference in the λ_{max} for the two solutions was found to be due to the acid in which the powdered sample of drug was dissolved. As all the reagents used were the same in both the methods and it was also found that temperature also maintained at the same for the two methods, the only

reason for the lower absorbance measurements for the latter was found to be the acid in which the drug samples solution was prepared.

The complete spectral data for piracetam was presented in Table 3. Table 4 gives a comparison between the standard method and the method proposed by the authors. The specific color reaction between the sample solution of drug, ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate was studied in the proposed method. In this method, aqueous solution of the drug on treatment with

Table 3. Spectral data analysis report for piracetam

Sr. No.	Name of the parameter	Method I
1.	Dissolution of the drug	Double distilled water
2.	Colour of the product	Intense blue
3.	Stability of the colored product (h)	24
4.	λ_{\max} (nm)	830
5.	Beer's law obedience ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0–60
6.	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.23
7.	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3.75
8.	Correlation	0.9897
9.	RSD (%)	1.4

Table 4. Comparison between the standard method and method developed by authors for piracetam

Sr. No.	Name of the drug	Method I		
		SM ^a (mg)	MU ^b (mg)	% error
1.	Alcetam	99.8	99.7	0.1
2.	Cebrazil	99.7	99.7	0
3.	Dalus Forte	99.5	99.4	0.1

^aStandard method. ^bMethod developed by author.

the above mentioned reagents, resulted in a molybdenum blue product, showing maximum absorbance at 830 nm (Fig. 4). Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range of 0–60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig. 5). Molar extinction coefficient for the same was found to be $3223.8 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ L cm}^{-1}$. Correlation coefficient in this method was found to be 0.9897, limit of detection was found to be $0.12 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and limit of quantification was found to be $0.39 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Relative standard deviation for ten samples was found to be 1.4% which was well within the standard value. In the method the reagents used were found to have no interference with the absorption spectra of the blue colored product.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectrum of the blue colored product obtained by the reaction between piracetam, ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate solutions.

Fig. 5. Beer's law obedience plot for the molybdenum blue complex obtained by the reaction between piracetam and ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate.

Normally used excipients such as starch, added flavors were found to have no interference with the absorption measurements. Use of phosphoric acid in the reaction was avoided, as it was reported to interfere in the reaction with molybdenum(VI)³⁵. The color reaction between the drug sample solution, ammonium molybdate solution and hydrazine sulphate solution was not observed in acetic acid, hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and nitric acid media. Addition of 5 ml of 2.5% ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of hydrazine sulphate solution was fixed as optimum volumes of the reagents being added to get stable, clear molybdenum blue complex.

Conclusions

Aqueous solution of the drug acetazolamide on reaction with ammonium molybdate and hydrazine sulphate,

formed molybdenum blue complex, showed a λ_{\max} at 830 nm, whereas the acidic solution of the drug showed a λ_{\max} at 824.5 nm. Beer's law obedience in Method I was found to be 0–80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and in Method II 0–40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, between the two methods developed by the authors it was found that Method I was advantageous over Method II for the reasons stated above. Aqueous solution of the drug piracetam on reaction with the specified reagents formed molybdenum blue complex, showed a λ_{\max} at 830 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the concentration range 0–80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The method is important in view of the fact that the excess dosage causes clinical problems and optimum dosage has to be fixed in the use of the drug.

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